

Deliverable 1.5

Guidelines for the implementation of a continuous EPC workflow

Lead Beneficiary: Jožef Stefan Institute (JSI)**Date:** 28.02.2022**Version:** 2.0**Dissemination level:** Publicwww.timepac.eu

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101033819.

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Document description

Deliverable No.	1.5
Dissemination level	Public
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Contributors	All consortium members have provided content for this document.
Due date of deliverable	28.02.2022
Actual submission date	31.05.2022

Version	Date	Beneficiary	Author
V0.1	31.10.2021	JSI	Boris Sučić
V0.2	03.11.2021	JSI	Gašper Stegnar
V0.3	20.05.2022	JSI	Boris Sučić
V0.4	23.05.2022	FUNITEC	Álvaro Sicilia
V0.5	26.05.2022	CUT	Alexandros Charalambides, Mariza Vryonidi (Internal review)
V0.6	26.05.2022	JSI	Boris Sučić
V0.7	27.05.2022	JSI	Boris Sučić
V1.0	31.05.2022	JSI	Boris Sučić
V2.0	11.10.2022	JSI	Paul McGuinness (proof-reading)

Table of contents

1 Introduction	5
1.1 Purpose and target group	5
1.2 Deliverable structure	6
1.3 Contribution of partners	6
1.4 Relations to other project activities	6
2 Generation	7
3 Storage	9
4 Analysis	11
5 Exploitation	12
6 Next steps	14
References	15

List of figures

Figure 1. A holistic approach to energy-performance assessment and the certification of buildings - continuous EPC data workflow connecting various stages and stakeholders in multiple ways.....	5
Figure 2. TIMEPAC approach to improving overall energy-performance assessment and certification of buildings	8
Figure 3. Complexity of the data-collection process during the EPC generation.....	9
Figure 4. Relationship between the outcomes of the analysis conducted in Task 1.3 and the objectives of the TDSs. Source: Deliverable 1.3 “Report on EPC data analysis”	11
Figure 5. Outline of the TIMEPAC methodology to improve EPC data exploitation	13

List of tables

Table 1. Improvements and challenges to be tackled in TDSs, DSs and TSs.....	14
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Executive Summary

This deliverable summarizes the results of Task 1.5 “Guidelines for the implementation of a continuous EPC workflow”, included in Work Package 1 (WP1) of the TIMEPAC project. The objective of WP1 is to conduct a comparative study of the elements involved in the development of future scenarios to work with an enhanced Energy Performance Certification (EPC) in each of the four identified stages of the EPC data flow: generation, storage, analysis and exploitation. As a result of this study, possible improvements, vulnerabilities, threats, and risks related to an upgrade of already-existing certification schemes have been identified.

Within WP1, the purpose of Task 1.5 is to analyse the findings and results of previous tasks (T1.1, 1.2, 1.3 and 1.4) and their applicability at the European level. In particular, the focus of the report is on identifying potential challenges to implement enhanced EPC schemes throughout the overall dataflow, encompassing generation, storage, analysis and exploitation.

Based on the outputs from Task 1.1 to Task 1.4, the following issues will be further addressed in the work to be conducted in the Transversal Deployment Scenarios (TDSs), Demonstration Scenarios (DSs) and Training Scenarios (TSs) to be carried out next in the TIMEPAC project:

- Data integration from various sources for more effective EPCs by considering the building as a whole (TDS1-4; DS1, DS3 and DS4; TS1, TS2 and TS6).
- EPC as a tool to support building renovation, integrating Building Renovation Passports (BRP) and Building Information Modelling (BIM) (TDS1 and TDS 3; DS3; TS3 and TS4).
- EPC enhancement with the Smart-Readiness Indicator and sustainability indicators to accelerate the creation of local, sustainable-energy communities (TDS4; DS2 and DS4; TS1 and TS4).
- Ensuring better EPC comparability among Member States (TDS5; DS1 and DS3; all TSs).
- Training activities and learning materials for EPC experts, building operators and energy service providers to use the enhanced EPC schemas (all TSs).

The know-how developed in these scenarios will be disseminated beyond the consortium through the TIMEPAC Academy. The training materials will focus on the practical application of the how-to-do approach in resolving existing problems in energy-performance certification. The main beneficiaries of the TIMEPAC Academy will be professional certifiers, national and regional standardisation bodies, energy and facility managers, and EPC experts.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and target group

A set of CEN standards¹ has been developed to ensure that the methodological framework stipulated by the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) concerning EPCs operates in a comparable way in all the Member States. However, practical experiences related to implementing the EPBD that are investigated in Task 1.1 revealed that effective compliance is far from evident, partly due to unclear technical procedures and different national implementation approaches.

The TIMEPAC approach is being built on the hypothesis that the certification process should not be thought of as a once-in-a-time event, but rather as part of a continuous data workflow connecting various stages and stakeholders in multiple ways during the building's lifetime: generation, storage, analysis and exploitation. Facilitating such a workflow would enable a more effective EPC and new services to exploit them (Figure 1).

Figure 1. A holistic approach to energy-performance assessment and the certification of buildings - continuous EPC data workflow connecting various stages and stakeholders in multiple ways

This report is the result of Task 1.5, “Guidelines for the implementation of a continuous EPC workflow”. The purpose of this task is to analyse the findings and results of the previous tasks (T1.1, 1.2, 1.3 and 1.4) and their applicability at the European level. The proposed approach will be further elaborated, demonstrated, and replicated through the Transversal Deployment Scenarios (TDSs), Demonstration Scenarios (DSs), and Training Scenarios (TSs). The focus of the work was to identify potential challenges to implement enhanced EPC schemes throughout the overall dataflow, encompassing generation, storage, analysis and exploitation.

This report provides a framework for proposing a unique EPC workflow that should facilitate dynamic certification over the EPC’s lifetime at the European level.

¹ In December 2010 the European Commission issued a Standardization Mandate M/480 to CEN, CENELEC, and ETSI for the elaboration and adoption of standards for a methodology calculating the integrated energy performance of buildings and promoting the energy efficiency of buildings. <https://epb.center/epb-standards/background/> (Accessed on April 15th 2022)

1.2 Deliverable structure

In addition to the introductory chapter, the document is made up of four additional chapters, each dedicated to one stage of the EPC data workflow:

- Generation
- Storage
- Analysis
- Exploitation

The main gaps and recommendations for each element of the EPC cycle are outlined in each chapter along with suggestions for how they will be used in the next steps of the project. The concluding chapter provides a summary of the essential findings and recommendations. References are given in a separate chapter.

1.3 Contribution of partners

The work carried out in the framework of Task 1.5 was coordinated by the Jožef Stefan Institute (JSI). With support from FUNITEC, POLITO, SERA, and CYPE, the JSI proposed a way in which the flow between the stages in the EPC cycle, in all directions, can be improved. With the support of MI, ICAEN, GOLEA, RP, SERA, CEA and CUT, the JSI provided additional features that should be included in the future exploitation of enhanced EPCs.

1.4 Relations to other project activities

The goal of this task is to draw conclusions from the work done in the four previous deliverables within WP1. It provides the starting point for the initial selection of buildings for TDSs and DSs, and for the definition of the training materials for the TSs. This deliverable's findings will also serve as a baseline for the new, enhanced certification schemes proposed in WP5.

2 Generation

This section presents a way in which the generation process can be improved to be effectively linked to the other three stages of the EPC cycle, i.e., storage, analysis and exploitation. In addition, connections with the proposed TDSs are indicated. From the theoretical point of view, an improved EPC must reflect a holistic overview of all the relevant indicators that could provide information that is pertinent to the building's owner or occupants about the actual and/or expected energy consumption. To improve the energy performance of buildings, it is necessary to follow an integrated approach, considering measures on both the building envelope and technical building systems. Unfortunately, the performance of some advanced or innovative technologies (e.g., building automation and control systems) is not accounted for in the evaluation tools, and EPC tools are not appropriately updated to consider the related energy savings. According to the latest proposal of the EPBD recast (2021), the energy performance of a building must be based on the calculated or the actual metered energy use. It must reflect typical energy use for space heating, space cooling, domestic hot water, ventilation, built-in lighting, and other technical building systems. For the EPC to be an effective tool for the analysis and improvement of the energy performance of buildings, the quality of the information it contains must be improved. This also underlines one of the major challenges of the TIMEPAC project and the need for necessary adaptations to the EPC generation workflow and the inclusion of actual energy-consumption data and targeted, specific energy-saving measures (for example, obtained from energy audits or technical inspection reports) into an enhanced EPC. Figure 2 represents an enhanced EPC generation workflow that includes the main findings and the recommendations from Task 1.1 "EPC Generation" (see Deliverable 1.1 "Context analysis of EPC generation").

The selection of the buildings for implementing TDS1 to TDS4 must reflect the need for additional data necessary for the generation of enhanced EPCs. For example, in TDS3 and TDS4, the available energy-audit reports for all the selected buildings will be critically reviewed to assess their applicability and to what extent their findings should be included in the building-renovation passports or be used to calculate the Smart Readiness Indicators (SRIs) and sustainability indicators in new and enhanced EPCs. In this context, buildings with energy-audit reports should be prioritised in the selection of the buildings to be used in these scenarios.

In the context of the generation and enhancement of EPCs with the implementation of a continuous workflow, the main challenge is how to incorporate the positive elements of all the identified approaches without making the EPC-generation process too complex and costly for the final users. During the implementation of the TDSs, these elements must be closely monitored and documented. The trade-off between extra costs and the obtained benefits must be objectively evaluated. In cases when a deep renovation is considered, the development of the BIM model could bring additional benefits to the end-user through better data quality and a more accurate energy simulation (Stegnar and Cervošek, 2019). In the context of the TIMEPAC project, special attention must be given to the training materials for the TIMEPAC Academy. The effectiveness of enhanced EPC relies on competent technicians who require additional training on assessing a building's energy performance and the creation of sound recommendations for the reduction of energy consumption.

TIMEPAC D1.5 - Generation

Figure 2. TIMEPAC approach to improving overall energy-performance assessment and certification of buildings

3 Storage

According to Arcipowska et al. (2014), by 2014, 24 EU countries will have established centralised EPC registries to store the certificates uploaded by an accredited assessor. However, in the majority of the countries, the EPC register is a decentralized application that is not connected to any other database that could bring added value to the EPC and improve the overall certification process, for example, energy management, BIM, and energy-utility databases. During the EPC generation process, especially in cases when the energy performance of complex buildings is being assessed, a vast amount of data is being processed. Figure 3 presents the complexity of the data-collection process.

Figure 3. Complexity of the data-collection process during the EPC generation

An analysis conducted in the framework of Task 1.2 “EPC data storage “revealed that the extent of data captured in XML files during the generation of the EPC is pervasive”. Even though the Open Data Directive (European Parliament and European Council, 2019) and Data Governance Act (European Parliament and European Council, 2020) encourage public administrations to adopt open-data policies, not all the EPC repositories audited in Task 1.2 are making their data available to citizen and third parties in this format due to conflict with possible data-privacy issues and the GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation).

Although EPC databases in all six TIMEPAC countries (Austria, Croatia, Cyprus, Italy, Slovenia, and Spain) are linked to, or are getting data from, the corresponding cadastre databases, there are still connections missing with other databases, such as BIM repositories, statistical databases and databases for the technical inspection of buildings. Interoperability between the different databases is crucial for an overall improvement of the EPC cycle since it significantly influences the accuracy of the EPC. The inadequate sharing of EPC data in terms of quantity and how it is shared (non-proprietary structured formats and FAIR principles) limits its reuse by the scientific community, citizens, and third parties in order that they can analyse it and create new services based on EPC data.

In TDS1 and TDS3 the data from BIM models and EPCs will be linked. As can be concluded from the results of the audit of the EPC databases (see Deliverable 1.2 “Comprehensive analysis of data storage in the participating countries”), none of the partner databases facilitated by partners are linked to a BIM database or include BIM data. TDS 2 will enhance EPC schemes using monitoring data (actual energy consumption, energy bills, etc.). There is only one case that offers the option to store monitoring data along with the EPC (Salzburg). The monitoring data will have to be collected from other sources in the remaining partner countries. EPC database managers can learn from Salzburg’s EPC database managers about storing and coping with monitoring data. The monitoring data will become part of the enhanced EPC schemes. TDS3 aims to generate BRP from the available data, such as EPC and BIM models. The case in this TDS is similar to TDS2, in which only Salzburg is already

storing elements of BRP data in the comprehensive database system. Again, EPC database managers can learn from Salzburg about how to store and cope with BRP data, using monitoring data together with the EPC. The database-complexity index is related to those TDSs that will analyse the database, such as TDS4 and TDS5. Having a less complex database schema will reduce the efforts required to update the schema to include new indicators (SRIs, sustainability indicators) and will ease the statistical analysis of the EPC databases. To have a comprehensive view of the building's performance, enhanced storage capabilities must make it possible to link EPC repositories to other buildings or energy-related databases as well as to data from various sources.

4 Analysis

According to Laustsen et al. (2011), the accuracy of EPC certification at the European level is estimated to be 35%. Research work presented by Majcen et al. (2014) and Durier et al. (2017) revealed that the biggest problem is the uncertainty of the data quality. Recent EPC data-quality surveys usually focus on data accuracy and consistency issues, which do not cover all levels of validation, as it is present (Simon, 2013). Therefore, these surveys do not reveal the difficulties that prevent the broader application of EPC data. According to Arcipowska et al. (2014), only 11 EU countries have carried out quality control for the EPC-calculation software using a calculation tool. In addition, 19 EU countries rely on the database for EPC quality control, supporting data verification, and random sampling (Arcipowska et al., 2014).

Research work conducted in Task 1.3 “EPC data analysis” revealed that the EPC data quality mainly depends on three factors:

- Validity of input data,
- EPC calculation methodology and applied tools,
- Assessor’s qualification.

Figure 4 presents the workflow of the research work conducted in Task 1.3. It outlines some key questions that will be answered in the TDSs by delivering specific methods, indicators and schemas.

Figure 4. Relationship between the outcomes of the analysis conducted in Task 1.3 and the objectives of the TDSs. Source: Deliverable 1.3 “Report on EPC data analysis”

The quality assurance of the input data is based on the technicians’ assessments and assumptions. Thus, a more efficient control system for the input data should be used to assure the accuracy of the inputs. Additional training for improving the competencies of the technicians in charge of carrying out the EPCs will have a positive influence on quality. This training will be tackled by the TIMEPAC Academy, in particular in TS2 “EPC data collection, validation, and exploitation” and TS3 “Advanced methods and tools for holistic energy renovation of buildings”.

5 Exploitation

One of the initial hypotheses of TIMEPAC is that EPCs can be an effective tool to encourage the refurbishment of buildings. A survey involving 12 EU countries revealed that 73% of the respondents consider EPC an essential driver for building renovation (Charalambides et al., 2019). Despite the perceived benefits of the EPC and the current adoption rates by policymakers, real-estate companies and research institutes, large-scale acceptance across the EU is still proving difficult. Previous studies have noted the following obstacles:

- A lack of data quality for energy-performance evaluations (Hardy and Glew, 2019).
- Insufficient information to motivate renovation (Christensen et al., 2014).
- Limited implementation to provide a robust information source for energy planning in some countries (Li et al., 2019).

An analysis conducted in Task 1.4 “Exploitation of EPC data” revealed that the use of BIM technology in architectural modelling and HVAC system design can contribute to improving the next generation of EPCs. The BIM model can be used to create the 3D architectural model of the project as well as the subsequent renovations of the building, as planned in the building-renovation passport. Additionally, BIM-based tools could become very useful for collecting and updating the overall information related to the buildings (e.g., the lifecycle of the building and the building’s components); however, there are still some interoperability problems present. To overcome them, during Task 1.4 it was concluded that TIMEPAC should provide a technical procedure to solve the interoperability problems between Building Information Modelling (BIM) tools and Building Energy Models (BEM) tools. The connection of BIM and EPC with HVAC system-design tools can also help to enrich existing EPC with information about the SRI and sustainability indicators. For example, a BIM model contains information about the surfaces and volumes of building spaces as well as more details about the thermal envelope of the building.

In addition to using BIM, TIMEPAC will adhere to the methodologies developed in the IEE projects TABULA and EPISCOPE. In TABULA, a building typology was created and applied to 13 European countries. Using a bottom-up approach, the building typology proved to be an effective way to carry out energy balances and refurbishment scenarios of building stocks on a large scale (Ballarini et al., 2011). In TIMEPAC, the quality of the EPCs will be improved by increasing the reliability of the data by applying quality-assurance methods to detect errors in the EPC generation. Moreover, the TABULA/EPISCOPE bottom-up approach will be upgraded to consider the transformation of the building over time in order to make the EPCs more dynamic. In addition, to increase the EPC reliability, factors that correlate the calculated energy use with the measured consumption will be developed, starting from the data collected on representative buildings.

TIMEPAC will also explore a methodology for the technical implementation of innovative data-handling features related to the quality assurance proposed in the X-tendo project (Maia et al., 2021). An outline of the TIMEPAC methodology to improve the exploitation of EPC data is presented in Figure 5.

6 Next steps

TIMEPAC's strategy based on the continuous flow of data through the four stages of the EPC cycle – generation, storage, analyses and exploitation – will be deployed using innovative procedures developed in six TDSs. These procedures will be based on an analysis of current practices in the TIMEPAC countries (Austria, Croatia, Cyprus, Italy, Slovenia and Spain) and adhere to current standards to assure their applicability across Europe. The innovative procedures developed in the six TDSs will be implemented in four DSs with the participation of diverse target groups. Strengthened and harmonised training materials will be collaboratively developed and facilitated through the TIMEPAC Academy. The training materials will focus on the practical application of the how-to-do approach to resolving existing problems in energy-performance certification. The main beneficiaries of the TIMEPAC Academy will be professional certifiers, national and regional standardisation bodies, energy and facility managers, and EPC experts.

Based on the outputs from Task 1.1, 1.2, 1.3 and 1.4, it has been proposed that the following improvement points and challenges related to the enhancement of EPCs and the implementation of a continuous workflow should be tackled through the implementation of TDSs, DSs and TSs (Table 1).

Table 1. Improvements and challenges to be tackled in TDSs, DSs and TSs

Improvements and challenges	TDS	DS	TS
Data integration from various sources for more effective EPCs, by considering the building as a whole	TDS1, 2, 3, and 4	DS3 and DS4	TS2 and TS6
EPC as a tool to support building renovation, integrating Building Renovation Passports (BRPs) and Building Information Modelling	TDS1 and TDS3	DS3	TS3 and TS4
EPC enhancement with a Smart Readiness Indicator and sustainability indicators to accelerate the creation of local sustainable-energy communities	TDS4	DS2 and DS4	TS1 and TS4
Ensuring better EPC comparability among Member States	TDS5	DS1 and DS3	all
Training activities and learning materials for EPC experts, building operators, and energy service providers to use the enhanced EPC schemas	-	-	all

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